

BINARY CYCLIC CODES FOR COMPLETE ZERO DIVISOR GRAPH OF A RING Z_n

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ABSTRACT

In this paper, let Z_n be the ring of integers modulo n . We define zero divisor graph $\Gamma(Z_n)$, when $n = p^a$, $a \geq 2$ and p is prime, which is complete. It is denoted by $K_n\Gamma(Z_n)$. We construct the binary cyclic codes for complete zero divisor graphs of a ring Z_n and generating matrix. Using these we find degree of the generating polynomial and dimension of the cyclic code C .

KEY WORDS: *Binary cyclic codes, Zero-Divisors, Zero-divisor graph, Complete graph, Adjacency matrix, Degree of the generating polynomials and Dimension of the cyclic code.*

I. INTRODUCTION

In 1948, Claude Shannon's landmark[1] was introduced cyclic codes in coding theory. In coding theory, a cyclic code is a block code, where the circular shifts of each codeword gives another word that belongs to the code. They are error-correcting codes that have algebraic properties that are convenient for efficient error detection and correction.

In abstract algebra, the theory of rings has its origin in the early 19th century when the commutative and non-commutative rings are being explored. A ring is one of the fundamental algebraic structures consisting of a set with two binary operations which are addition and multiplication [2].

In 1988, the zero-divisor graph was first introduced by Beck [2]. Beck introduced idea of presenting zero-divisor graph of a commutative ring R in 1988 and its zero-divisor graph $G(R)$ whose vertices are the zero-divisors of R (including 0) and two distinct vertices a and b are adjacent if and only if $ab = 0$. Anderson and Livingston [1] introduced and studied the subgraph $\Gamma(R)$ (of $G(R)$) whose vertices are the non-zero zero-divisors of R and the authors studied the interplay between the ring-theoretic properties of a commutative ring and the graph theoretic properties of its zero-divisor graph. Let $Z^*(R) = Z(R) \setminus (0)$, be the set of non-zero zero-divisors of R . The zero-divisor graph of R , denoted by $\Gamma(R)$, is a simple undirected graph with all non-zero zero-divisors as vertices and two distinct vertices $x, y \in Z^*(R)$ are adjacent if and only if $xy = 0$. Thus $\Gamma(R)$ is the null graph if and only if R is an integral domain. Mohammed Reza Ahmadi and Reza Jahani-Nehad [6] studied the energy and Wiener index of the zero divisor graph for the ring of integers modulo n , for $n = p^2$, $n = pq$, where p and q are distinct

prime numbers. Shaik.Sajana and Dr.D.Bharathi studied, the intersection of zero divisors of a commutative ring[7].

Let R be a commutative ring with identity and let $Z(R)$ be the set of zero- divisors of R . We associate a simple graph $\Gamma(R)$ to R with non-zero zero divisor vertices $Z^*(R)=Z(R)-\{0\}$ the set of non-zero zero divisors of R , and for distinct $x, y \in Z^*(R)$, the vertices x and y are adjacent if and only if $xy = 0$ as zero divisor elements. Note that $\Gamma(R)$ is empty if and only if R is an integral domain, and the zero divisor graph is always simple undirected complete graph.

Let Z_n be the ring of integers modulo n . The zero-divisor graph of Z_n , denoted by $\Gamma(Z_n)$, is the graph with vertex set $V(\Gamma(Z_n))$ and for distinct vertices a and b are adjacent if and only if $a.b = 0 \pmod{n}$. Clearly, $\Gamma(Z_n)$ is the null graph if and only if Z_n is an integral domain.

II. PRELIMINARIES

Related to Coding theory:

- A **code** is a set of codewords.
- A **binary code** is a code over the alphabet $\{0, 1\}$
- A binary code is **cyclic code** if it is a linear $[n, k]$ code and if for every codeword $(c_1, c_2, \dots, c_n) \in C$ we also have that $(c_n, c_1, \dots, c_{n-1})$ is again a codeword in C
- **Binary cyclic codes** are a type of error-correcting code that is used in digital communications. They are characterized by the fact that they are cyclic, meaning that the codeword can be cyclically shifted by any number of positions and still be a valid codeword.
- The **adjacency matrix** of a undirected graph G is the matrix $A(G)$ with rows and columns indexed by vertices of G . Each entry ij is equal to the number of times the arc (i, j) appears in G . The adjacency matrix of a complete graph has a pleasing nature : each row is the cyclic shift of the preceding row. If (a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n) is the first row, then $(a_n, a_1, \dots, a_{n-1})$ is the second row $(a_{n-1}, a_n, \dots, a_{n-2})$ is the third row and finally (a_2, a_3, \dots, a_1) is the n th row.

If F represents the binary field, then F^n the set of all n -tuples of F is an n -dimensional vector space over F . A k -dimensional subspace of F^n is called an $[n,k]$ binary linear code C . A basis of C consists of k linearly independent binary n -tuples. The matrix formed by the basis vectors is called a generator matrix of C . The elements of C are called codewords and are linear combinations of the rows of the generator matrix. Since a vector space can have many bases, a code C has many generator matrices.

An $[n,k]$ code C is called cyclic if whenever $x = (a_0, a_1, \dots, a_{n-1})$ is in C , so is its first cyclic shift $y = (a_{n-1}, a_0, \dots, a_{n-2})$. This means that $(a_{n-2}, a_{n-1}, \dots, a_{n-3})$ the first cyclic shift of y and all other cyclic shifts of y are also in C . When considering cyclic codes it is useful to let a vector $(a_0, a_1, \dots, a_{n-1})$ corresponds to a polynomial $a_0 + a_1x + \dots + a_{n-1}x^{n-1}$. Then $(a_{n-1}, a_0, \dots, a_{n-2})$. corresponds to $a_{n-1} + a_0x + \dots + a_{n-2}x^{n-1}$. This polynomial equals the polynomial $a_0 + a_1x + \dots + a_{n-1}x^{n-1}x \pmod{x^n + 1}$.

Hence the cyclic shift corresponds to multiplication by x . If $F[x]$ represents the ring of polynomials over F , then the set $R_n[x] = \frac{F[x]}{(x^n + 1)}$ consists of polynomials over F of degree less than n is a ring. Polynomials in R_n are added co-ordinate wise and multiplication is modulo $(x^n + 1)$.

- The matrix G has n columns and $k = n - r$ rows. Each row is the cyclic shift of the previous row. Since $g(x)h(x) = x^n + 1$, G is in echelon form, its rows are linearly independent thus $k = n - r$ is the **dimension of the code** generated by G .
- Degree of a polynomial cyclic code is $\deg k(x) = n - k$.
- Dimension of a cyclic code C is k and cyclic code C of length n contains all n cyclic shifts of any codeword.

Ring theoretic preliminaries:

- A ring R is a nonempty set together with two binary operation $+$ and \cdot (called addition and multiplication defined on R) satisfying the following axioms:
 - $(R, +)$ is an abelian group,
 - (R, \cdot) is semi-group,
 - The distributive laws hold in R

Ex: $(\mathbb{Z}_n, \oplus, \odot)$ is a ring,

- A non-zero element a in a ring R is called a zero divisor if there exists $b \in R$ such that $b \neq 0$ and $ab = 0$. In particular, a is a left divisor of zero and b is a right divisor of zero .
- In the ring $\mathbb{Z}_6 = \{0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5\}$ Since $2 \cdot 3 = 6 = 0$ $3 \cdot 4 = 12 = 0$, then 2,3,4 are non-zero zero divisors of \mathbb{Z}_6 .
- $|\mathbb{Z}^*(R)| =$ The no. of non-zero zero divisors.

Graph theoretic preliminaries:

- A **graph** $G = (V, E)$ consists of a set V of vertices (also called nodes) and a set E of edges
- An **undirected graph** is a type of graph where the edges have no specified direction assigned to the them.
- The **degree of a vertex** is the number of edges incident to that vertex and is denoted by $\deg(v)$.
- A graph is said to be **connected** if every pair of vertices in the graph is connected. This means that there is a path between every pair of vertices.
- The **complete graph** on m nodes, denoted by K_m , is the simple graph with nodes $\{1, \dots, m\}$ and an edge is between every pair of distinct nodes.
- A **connected** graph is a graph where every pair of vertices is connected by a path. A path is a sequence of edges that connects two distinct vertices.
- **Zero-Divisor Graph** is an undirected graph representing the zero divisors of a commutative ring as vertex set and pairs of elements whose product is zero as its edges.

III. MAIN SECTION

CONSTRUCTION OF BINARY CYCLIC CODES FOR COMPLETE ZERO-DIVISOR GRAPHS OF A RING Z_n :

The set of vertices of G form an adjacency matrix X of G and $g(x)$ is the monic polynomial of smallest degree in G , then $g(x)$ is uniquely determined and the code $C = \langle g(x) \rangle$.

- The unique monic polynomial $g(x)$ of the smallest degree in G is called the **generator polynomial** of C .

The unique generator $g(x)$ of C of smallest degree divides $(x^n + 1)$ and conversely if a polynomial $g(x)$ in C divides $(x^n + 1)$, then $g(x)$, the lowest degree polynomial becomes generating polynomial of G .

- When considering binary cyclic codes, we here assume that n is even of the form $x^n + 1$ have same factors.
- Note that when n is odd $x^n + 1$ has distinct factors.

There is a nice relationship between the dimension of a cyclic code and the degree of its generator polynomial are related by the following theorem

Theorem 3.1.1: For a prime number, the graph for $\Gamma(Z_p)$ does not exist.

Proof: For any prime p , Z_p is a field.

Therefore, Z_p has no zero divisors. It is clear that the vertex set of the graph $\Gamma(Z_n)$ is empty, and thus the graph $\Gamma(Z_n)$ does not exist.

- In this paper, we prove that for every positive integer n and every prime p , the zero divisor graph $\Gamma(Z_n)$ holds the following.

(i). $\Gamma(Z_n) = \emptyset$, then $n = p$

(ii). $\Gamma(Z_n) \neq \emptyset$, then $n = p^a$ with $a \geq 2$

(iii). $\Gamma(Z_n) \neq \emptyset$, then $n = p_1 p_2 \dots p_m$ with $m \geq 2$

Theorem 3.1.2: Suppose $K_m(\Gamma(Z_n))$ is a complete zero divisor graph of a ring Z_n . Let C be the binary cyclic code representing X . Then $g(x) = \gcd(c(x), x^n + 1)$ is the generator polynomial of C and $C = \langle c(x) \rangle$. If $\langle g(x) \rangle$ has degree $m - k$, then $\dim C = k$.

Proof: Let $C = \langle c(x) \rangle$ be the binary cyclic code representing X . where $c(x)$ is the first row of the adjacency matrix of X .

We first prove that $c(x)$ is a linear combination of $g(x)$ and its cyclic shifts and that $g(x)$ is a linear combination of $c(x)$ and its cyclic shifts.

Since $g(x) = \gcd(c(x), x^n + 1)$.

Therefore $c(x) = a(x)g(x)$ for some $a(x) \in R_n[x]$

If $g(x)$ has degree $n - k$, then $g(x), xg(x), \dots, x^{k-1}g(x)$ is linearly independent set.

If $a(x) = a_0 + a_1x + a_2x^2 + \dots + a_{k-1}x^{k-1}$,

we have $c(x) = a(x)g(x) = a_0g(x) + a_1xg(x) + a_2x^2g(x) + \dots + a_{n-1}x^{n-1}g(x)$

Thus $c(x)$ is a linear combination of $g(x)$ and its cyclic shifts.

Again, since $g(x) = \gcd(c(x), x^n + 1)$

By Euclidean division algorithm, $c(x) = h(x)g(x) + r(x)(x^n + 1)$ in $F_n[x]$.

Since $c(x)$ and $g(x)$ are codewords of C .

Therefore, $r(x) \in C$, either $r(x) = 0$ or $\deg r(x) < \deg g(x)$.

This is impossible. So, $r(x) = 0$

Since $g(x)$ is the smallest degree polynomial.

Hence $g(x)$ is a divisor of every codeword in C in C .

Therefore $C = \langle g(x) \rangle$. (Since $g(x) / x^m + 1$ is a cyclic code.

Finally, $g(x)$ has degree $m - k$ and the dimension of $C = k$.

Theorem 3.1.3: The zero divisor graph $\Gamma(Z_n)$ is complete, when the order of non-zero zero divisors is even and when $n = p^a$, $a \geq 2$.

Proof: Let Z_n be the ring of integers modulo n and $\Gamma(Z_n)$ is the non-zero zero-divisor graph of Z_n .

To prove, the graph $\Gamma(Z_n)$ is complete, when the order of non-zero zero divisors is even and $n = p^a$, $a \geq 2$.

By the definition of Zero divisor graph, if u and v be in $V(\Gamma(Z_n))$, then $u.v \equiv 0 \pmod{n}$

The order of the graph $\Gamma(Z_n) = n - \phi(n) - 1 = m$, here we take m is even.

The vertex set is defined as $V(\Gamma(Z_n)) = \{u \in Z_n / u \text{ is a non-zero zero divisor of } Z_n\}$.

The edge set is defined as $\{uv / u, v \in V(\Gamma(Z_n)) \text{ and } u.v \equiv 0 \pmod{n}\}$

By [7], The no. of edges is $|E(\Gamma(Z_n))| = (p^{a-1} - 1)(p^{a-1} - 2) / 2 = \binom{n - \phi(n) - 1}{2}$

This shows that, the each vertex in the set V is adjacent with all the vertices u in $\Gamma(Z_n)$.

Hence, the graph $\Gamma(Z_n)$ forms a complete graph. It is denoted by $K_m(\Gamma(Z_n))$. Here m denotes the no. of vertices of $\Gamma(Z_n)$, whose vertex set has even no. of non-zero zero divisors of complete graph. ■

From graph, the adjacency matrix of a graph $K_m(\Gamma(Z_n))$ is

$$= \begin{bmatrix} 0 & g_0 & g_1 & \dots & g_{m-1} \\ g_{m-1} & 0 & g_0 & g_1 & g_{m-2} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ g_0 & g_1 & \dots & \dots & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$

Let C denotes the set of codewords, $C = \{0, g_0, \dots, g_{m-1}\}$, Where $C_1 = \{g_{m-1}, 0, g_0, \dots, g_{m-2}\}$, and $C_n = \{g_0, g_1, \dots, g_{m-1}, 0\}$.

From the theorem 3.1.2, C is a binary cyclic code

Similarly, we can find the cyclic codes of length $n = p^a$, $a \geq 2$ generated by the even no.of non-zero zero divisors of the corresponding commutative ring.

Theorem 3.1.4: If C is a binary cyclic code of length m, then C corresponds to a complete graph on $K_m \Gamma(Z_n)$. Conversely if $K_m \Gamma(Z_n)$ is a complete zero divisor graph of a ring Z_n , then C corresponds to a binary cyclic code. ■

- We find binary cyclic code C for Z_9 and Basis for C.

Example 3.1.6: $Z_9 = \{0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8\}$

In Z_9 , the non-zero zero-divisors are 3 and 6.

The no.of zero divisors of $Z_n = n - \varphi(n) - 1 = m$

Here $\varphi(n) =$ positive integer less than n and relatively prime to n.

$$= n \prod_{p|n} (1 - 1/p)$$

$$\varphi(9) = 9(1 - 1/3) = 6$$

The no.of zero divisors of $Z_9 = 9 - 6 - 1 = 2$, even

The set of non-zero zero divisors of Z_9 is $V(\Gamma(Z_9)) = \{3, 6\}$.

Since $3 \cdot 6 \equiv 0 \pmod{9}$, each of these elements is connected to each other in the zero-divisor graph. The set of edges of $\Gamma(Z_9)$ is $E(\Gamma(Z_9)) = \{(3, 6)\}$

$\Gamma(Z_9)$ Figure 3.1

The degree of each vertex = $d(3) = d(6) = 1$

The sum of all degree of vertices = $2(2-1) = 2$.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{The no.of edges of the graph } |E(\Gamma(Z_n))| &= \frac{(p^{a-1} - 1)(p^{a-1} - 2)}{2} ; \text{ Here } p=3 \text{ and } a=2 \\ &= \frac{(3^{2-1} - 1)(3^{2-1} - 2)}{2} \\ &= \frac{(3-1)(3-2)}{2} \\ &= \frac{2(1)}{2} \\ &= 1 \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, $\Gamma(Z_9)$ is complete graph, $K_2(\Gamma(Z_9))$

Code of the vertices $c_1 = 01, c_2 = 10$

Code of the $K_2(\Gamma(Z_9)) = C = \{01, 10\}$.

The adjacency matrix of X is $\begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \sim \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$

The generating polynomial $g(x)$ is of minimum dedgree.

Therefore, $g(x) = 1$

Hence X corresponds to the cyclic code $C = \langle c(x) \rangle$

Length of the code = $n = 2$.

Since the degree of the generator polynomial $g(x) = 0$, dimension of the code = $2 - 0 = 2$, then the basis for $C = \{10, 01\}$

Theorem 3.1.5: The zero divisor graph $\Gamma(Z_{p^3})$ is complete, when the order of non-zero zero divisors is even and $a \geq 3$.

Proof: From the theorem 3.1 4 and theorem 3.1.5.

Example 3.1.8: $Z_{27} = \{0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, \dots, 26\}$

In Z_{27} , the non-zero zero-divisors are 3, 6, 9, 12, 15, 18, 21 and 24.

The no.of zero divisors of $Z_n = n - \varphi(n) - 1$

Here $\varphi(n) =$ positive integer less than n and relatively prime to n .

$$= n \prod_{p|n} (1 - 1/p)$$

$$\varphi(27) = 27(1 - 1/3) = 18$$

The no.of zero divisors of $Z_{27} = 27 - 18 - 1 = 8$, even.

The set of non-zero zero divisors of Z_{27} is $V(\Gamma(Z_{27})) = \{3, 6, 9, 12, 15, 18, 21, 24\}$.

Since $9 \cdot 6 \equiv 0 \pmod{27}$ and similarly for the other combinations, each of these elements is connected to each other in the zero-divisor graph.

The set of edges of $\Gamma(Z_{27})$ is

$E(\Gamma(Z_{27})) = \{(3,6), (6,9), (9,12), (12,15), (15,18), (18,21), (21,24), (24,3), (3,9), (9,15), (15,21), (21,3), (6,12), (12,18), (18,24), (24,6), (3,12), (12,21), (21,6), (6,15), (15,24), (24,9), (9,18), (18,3), (18,9), (9,24), (24,15), (15,3)\}$

$\Gamma(Z_{27})$ Figure 3.2

The degree of each vertex is $(n-1) = d(3)=d(6)=d(9)=d(12)=d(15)=d(18)=d(21)=d(24)=7$

The sum of all degree of vertices = $n(n-1) = 8(8-1)=56$.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{The no.of edges of the graph } |E(\Gamma(Z_n))| &= \frac{(p^{a-1} - 1)(p^{a-1} - 2)}{2} ; \text{ Here } p=3 \text{ and } a=3 \\ &= \frac{(3^{3-1} - 1)(3^{3-1} - 2)}{2} \\ &= \frac{(3^2 - 1)(3^2 - 2)}{2} \\ &= \frac{8(7)}{2} = 56 / 2 = 28 \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, $\Gamma(Z_{27})$ is complete graph, $K_8(\Gamma(Z_{27}))$

Code of the vertices $c_1 = 0111111$, $c_2 = 10111111$, $c_3=11011111$, $c_4=11101111$, $c_5=11110111$, $c_6=11111011$, $c_7=11111101$, $c_8=11111110$

Code of the $K_8(\Gamma(Z_{27})) = C = \{01111111, 10111111, 11011111, 11101111, 11110111, 11111011, 11111101, 11111110\}$.

The adjacency matrix of X is

$$\begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 1 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \sim \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$$

The polynomial represented by X is $g(x) = 1+x$

Hence X corresponds to the cyclic code $C = \langle c(x) \rangle$

Length of the code = $n = 8$.

Since the degree of the generator polynomial $g(x) = 1$, dimension of the code = 7, then the basis for $C = \{1100000, 0110000, 0011000, 0001100, 0000110, 0000011\}$.

Theorem 3.1.6: The zero divisor graph $K_m(\Gamma(Z_n))$ is not complete. If the following conditions hold

(i). If $n = pq$, $p^a q$, pq^a , $p^a q^b$; $p, q \geq 2$ and $a, b \geq 1$, when a, b are two positive integers and p, q are two different primes.

(ii). If n is the product of at least two prime powers.

Proof: From theorem 3.1.5, in each case, the graph $K_m\Gamma(Z_n)$ is not a complete zero divisor graph.

Example 3.1.7: The zero divisor graph $\Gamma(Z_6)$ is not complete.

In $\Gamma(Z_{pq}) = \Gamma(Z_{2 \times 3}) = \Gamma(Z_6)$, $Z_6 = \{0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5\}$

In Z_6 , the non-zero zero-divisors are 2, 3 and 4.

Since $2 \cdot 3 \equiv 0 \pmod{6}$, $2 \cdot 4 \not\equiv 0 \pmod{6}$ 2 and 4 are not adjacent implies $\Gamma(Z_{pq})$ does not form complete graph.

$\Gamma(Z_6)$ Figure 3.3

The adjacency matrix X is $\begin{bmatrix} 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \sim \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$, it is not a cyclic code.

Example 3.1.8: The zero divisor graph $\Gamma(Z_{12})$ is not complete.

In $\Gamma(Z_{p^n q}) = \Gamma(Z_{2^2 \times 3}) = \Gamma(Z_{12})$, $Z_{12} = \{0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11\}$

In Z_{12} , the non-zero zero-divisors are 2, 3, 4, 6, 8, 9 and 10.

Since $2 \cdot 6 \equiv 0 \pmod{12}$, $3 \cdot 4 \equiv 0 \pmod{12}$, $8 \cdot 3 \equiv 0 \pmod{12}$, $4 \cdot 6 \equiv 0 \pmod{12}$, $9 \cdot 4 \equiv 0 \pmod{12}$, $6 \cdot 10 \equiv 0 \pmod{12}$, $6 \cdot 8 \equiv 0 \pmod{12}$ and $8 \cdot 9 \equiv 0 \pmod{12}$ and $9 \cdot 10 \not\equiv 0 \pmod{12}$ 9 and 10 are not adjacent and similarly for the other combinations. i.e., adjacency for some pair of vertices does not exist.

Therefore, $\Gamma(Z_{12})$ does not form complete graph.

$\Gamma(Z_{12})$ Figure 3.4

The adjacency matrix X is
$$\begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$
, it is not a cyclic code.

Example 3.1.9: The zero divisor graph $\Gamma(Z_{18})$ is not complete.

In $\Gamma(Z_{pq}) = \Gamma(Z_2 \cdot 3^2) = \Gamma(Z_{18})$, $Z_{18} = \{0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, \dots, 17\}$

In Z_{18} , the non-zero zero-divisors are 2, 3, 4, 6, 8, 9, 10, 12, 14, 15 and 16.

Since $2 \cdot 9 \equiv 0 \pmod{18}$, $3 \cdot 6 \equiv 0 \pmod{18}$, $12 \cdot 30 \equiv 0 \pmod{18}$, $4 \cdot 9 \equiv 0 \pmod{18}$, $6 \cdot 9 \equiv 0 \pmod{18}$, $6 \cdot 12 \equiv 0 \pmod{18}$, $6 \cdot 15 \equiv 0 \pmod{18}$, $9 \cdot 10 \equiv 0 \pmod{18}$, $8 \cdot 9 \equiv 0 \pmod{18}$, $9 \cdot 12 \equiv 0 \pmod{18}$, $9 \cdot 14 \equiv 0 \pmod{18}$, $9 \cdot 16 \equiv 0 \pmod{18}$, $12 \cdot 15 \equiv 0 \pmod{18}$ and $2 \cdot 3 \equiv 0 \pmod{18}$, $2 \cdot 9 \neq 0 \pmod{18}$, $2 \cdot 4 \neq 0 \pmod{18}$, similarly for the other combinations. i.e., adjacency for some pair of vertices does not exist.

$\Gamma(Z_{pq}) = \Gamma(Z_2 \cdot 3^2) = \Gamma(Z_{18})$ does not form complete graph.

$\Gamma(Z_{18})$ Figure 3.5

The adjacency matrix X is
$$\begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix}$$
, it is not a cyclic code.

Example 3.1.10: The zero divisor graph $\Gamma(Z_{36})$ is not complete.

In $\Gamma(Z_p^a) = \Gamma(Z_2^2 \cdot 3^2) = \Gamma(Z_{36})$, $Z_{36} = \{0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, \dots, 35\}$

In Z_{18} , the non-zero zero-divisors are 2, 3, 4, 6, 8, 9, 10, 12, 14, 15, 16, 18, 20, 21, 22, 24, 26, 27, 28, 30, 32, 33, and 34.

Since $2 \cdot 18 \equiv 0 \pmod{36}$, $3 \cdot 12 \equiv 0 \pmod{36}$, $3 \cdot 18 \equiv 0 \pmod{36}$, $4 \cdot 9 \equiv 0 \pmod{36}$, $6 \cdot 12 \equiv 0 \pmod{36}$, $6 \cdot 18 \equiv 0 \pmod{36}$, $6 \cdot 24 \equiv 0 \pmod{36}$, $6 \cdot 30 \equiv 0 \pmod{36}$, $8 \cdot 18 \equiv 0 \pmod{36}$, $8 \cdot 27 \equiv 0 \pmod{36}$, $9 \cdot 12 \equiv 0 \pmod{36}$, $9 \cdot 16 \equiv 0 \pmod{36}$, $9 \cdot 20 \equiv 0 \pmod{36}$, $9 \cdot 24 \equiv 0 \pmod{36}$, $9 \cdot 27 \equiv 0 \pmod{36}$, $9 \cdot 32 \equiv 0 \pmod{36}$, $10 \cdot 18 \equiv 0 \pmod{36}$, $12 \cdot 15 \equiv 0 \pmod{36}$, $12 \cdot 18 \equiv 0 \pmod{36}$, $12 \cdot 21 \equiv 0 \pmod{36}$, $12 \cdot 24 \equiv 0 \pmod{36}$, $12 \cdot 28 \equiv 0 \pmod{36}$, $12 \cdot 30 \equiv 0 \pmod{36}$, $12 \cdot 33 \equiv 0 \pmod{36}$, $14 \cdot 18 \equiv 0 \pmod{36}$, $15 \cdot 24 \equiv 0 \pmod{36}$, $16 \cdot 18 \equiv 0 \pmod{36}$, $18 \cdot 20 \equiv 0 \pmod{36}$, $18 \cdot 22 \equiv 0 \pmod{36}$, $18 \cdot 24 \equiv 0 \pmod{36}$, $18 \cdot 26 \equiv 0 \pmod{36}$, $18 \cdot 28 \equiv 0 \pmod{36}$, $18 \cdot 30 \equiv 0 \pmod{36}$, $18 \cdot 32 \equiv 0 \pmod{36}$, $18 \cdot 34 \equiv 0 \pmod{36}$, $21 \cdot 24 \equiv 0 \pmod{36}$, $24 \cdot 30 \equiv 0 \pmod{36}$, $24 \cdot 30 \equiv 0 \pmod{36}$ and $2 \cdot 3 \not\equiv 0 \pmod{36}$, $3 \cdot 6 \not\equiv 0 \pmod{36}$, similarly for the other combinations. i.e. adjacency for some pair of vertices does not exist.

Therefore, $\Gamma(Z_p^a) = \Gamma(Z_2^2 \cdot 3^2) = \Gamma(Z_{36})$ does not form complete graph.

$\Gamma(Z_{36})$ Figure 3.6

The adjacency matrix $\Gamma(Z_{36})$ of X is not a cyclic code.

CONCLUSIONS

1. We constructed the binary cyclic codes of complete zero-divisor graphs of a ring Z_n , when $n = p^a$; prime p and $a \geq 2$.

- The complete zero divisor graph for $\Gamma(Z_p)$ does not exist. i.e, for $a=1$.
- The complete zero divisor graph $K_m(\Gamma(Z_p^a))$ exists, when $m = |\Gamma(Z_p^a)|$, a is even and $a \geq 2$.

2. The zero divisor graph $\Gamma(Z_n)$ is not complete. If the following conditions hold

- (i). If $n = p^a q^b$; $p, q \geq 2$ and $a, b \geq 1$, when a, b are two positive integers and p, q are two different primes.
- (ii). If n is the product of at least two prime powers.

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